

YIELDING BEHAVIOUR OF A MODEL EPOXY RESIN MATRIX FOR FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The effect of yielding of a polymer matrix on stress transfer between a broken fibre and an adjacent fibre has been studied using a three-dimensional finite element model. The yield behaviour of triglycidyl *p*-aminophenol, TGAP (Araldite MY0510) epoxy resin cured with DDS hardener has been investigated as a function of temperature and strain rate. The compressive yield strength increased as the strain rate increased. An inverse trend was observed at high temperatures for compressive yield strength and modulus. The full elasto-plastic stress-strain curves of the epoxy resin at a range of temperatures have been included in a 3D multi-fibre FE model. The yielding of the matrix as a function of the temperature affects the axial strain development along both the fractured and the neighbouring fibre. The intensified axial strain at the intact neighbouring fibre has been found at the immediate radial distance from the broken fibre. Strain concentration Factor (SCF) of nearest neighbouring fibre decreased because of an increase in temperature.

KEYWORDS: Epoxy resin, Yielding, Uniaxial compression, Temperature, Strain rate, FEA, Fibre-break, Strain concentration factor.

INTRODUCTION

Since the properties of composite materials can be dominated by those of the matrices, their key properties should be identified and characterised to provide a link with the macroscopic mechanical behaviour of a unidirectional fibre reinforced composite. It is generally believed that unidirectional composite materials mostly fail by in-plane fibre fracture. Therefore, the redistribution of the stress between the intact fibres adjacent to a broken fibre is a governing mechanism in the ultimate composite strength. With perfect matrix/fibre bonding, yielding of the elasto-plastic matrix that surrounds a broken fibre can alter the probability of sub segment fracture of the adjacent fibres and eventually of the composite material [1]. As the matrix at the vicinity of a broken fibre absorbs energy to deform plastically, it reduces the stress concentration on the intact adjacent fibres to establish energy equilibrium.

Most of the models [2,3] for predicting the strain (or stress) concentration factor (SCF) in the adjacent intact fibres to a fibre-fracture neglect the non-linearity (elasto-plasticity) of the matrix, which is assumed to be a linear elastic material. This limits predictive accuracy of the models. However, Hedgepeth and van Dyke [4] reported the presence of plasticity in their work, which resulted in a decrease in stress concentration with increase in load. On the other hand, the elasto-plasticity has been incorporated into some finite element models [1,5], which led to a significant decrease in strain concentration factor. In contrast, it has been shown elsewhere [6] that matrix plasticity resulted in a slight decrease in the SCF and it was

considered that the SCF was affected more by the number of surrounding fibres. However, the inclusion of matrix plasticity into the FE model should result in a value of SCF which is in a good agreement with experiment.

Thus, in the current study, the yield strength of the epoxy resin, which is a key mechanism for controlling the matrix-to-fibre stress transfer, was identified as the principal matrix property to determine the probability of failure of a 0° fibre composite. It could then be used to predict the stress concentration in an adjacent fibre to a fibre-break, and provide a predictive tool for the optimisation of composite performance through matrix selection and the effect of moisture absorption.

Epoxy resins are one of the most important thermosetting polymers which have been extensively used in aerospace composites materials over last few decades because of their high yield strength, Young's moduli and glass transition temperature. As a viscoelastic material, the yielding behaviour of an epoxy resin is extremely dependent on time and temperature. According to Eyring's theory of viscosity [7], yielding occurs by stress-activated jumps of molecular segments known as flow units. Applying a stress effectively lowers the activation barrier for these jumps which leads to a coordinated motion known as yielding. Similarly, at a higher strain rate there is a higher molecular resistance to jumps and hence a higher yield stress.

Similar effects of testing rate and temperature on epoxy resin networks have been reported by several authors [8-17]. However, no attempt to characterize the yielding behaviour of high glass transition temperature epoxy resins used in high performance fibre composites has been made. However, most work is focused on a crosslinked difunctional (DGEBA) epoxy resin.

Yielding in highly crosslinked resins is not a very explicable concept because of the low mobility of molecular network chains which leads to brittleness at low strains. Thus under a tensile stress, thermosetting resins fracture at strains far below their yield strain, but under uniaxial compression undergo considerable plastic deformation. Therefore, in this paper we report a study of the yield behaviour of typical commercial epoxy resins under a compressive load, at a range of strain rates and temperatures.

EXPERIMENTAL

The epoxy resin monomer used for this study is triglycidyl *p*-aminophenol (TGAP), Araldite MY0510[®] which mainly is used for high performance composites. It was kindly supplied by ACG Ltd UK, and used without further purification. The epoxy resin was cured with 4-4'-diaminodiphenyl sulphone, DDS hardener (Lancaster synthesis, UK). The chemical structures are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Chemical structures of TGAP epoxy resin and DDS hardener.

The epoxy resin was cured with DDS at a composition shown in Table 1. DDS was dissolved in the epoxy resin by vigorous stirring at 120 °C for 10 minutes before degassing in a vacuum oven for 30 minutes. In order to prepare cylindrical shaped specimens suitable for uniaxial compression testing, the mixture was then poured into a preheated cylindrically shaped PTFE mould with the interior dimensions of 30 mm × 10 mm. A PTFE mould release agent was found to facilitate the specimen's removal from the cavity. The specimens were cured at 130 °C for 1 hour followed by postcuring at 180 °C for 2 hours before cooling down in the oven overnight. The cast specimens were carefully machined on a lathe to achieve a length-to-diameter ratio of 1:1 (10 mm/10mm).

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) was used to obtain the degree of cure of the epoxy resin. The degree of conversion of epoxy groups, degree of cure, was defined as:

$$C = 1 - \Delta H_r / \Delta H_T \quad (2)$$

where ΔH_r is the residual enthalpy for curing and ΔH_T is the total heat evolved by an epoxy-amine reaction. The estimated degree of conversion has been listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Composition, degree of conversion and glass transition temperature of epoxy resin.

Epoxy Resin system	MY0510/DDS
Hardener DDS wt.(%)	36
Conversion	0.93
T_g (°C) ^[18]	285

Uniaxial compression testing of the cylindrical specimens was performed with a Hounsfield universal testing instrument using a load cell of 100 kN. The crossheads and the specimen ends were smeared with a touch of petroleum jelly before alignment to minimise the frictional forces at the junctions. Fig. 2 shows a schematic to illustrate the uniaxial compression procedure where the lack of barrelling is also indicated.

Fig. 2: Schematic compression progress on a cylindrical specimen before and after applying the load.

At least five specimens were tested at a range of temperatures between 20 °C (\approx RT) to 180 °C and at strain rates varying from 1.67×10^{-4} to $1.67 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The true strain ϵ_T and stress σ_T was determined by:

$$\epsilon_T = \ln (L_i/L_o) \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma_T = F / [A_o \exp(\epsilon_T)] \quad (6)$$

where L_i and L_t , F and A_0 are the initial and instantaneous length, load and the initial cross-sectional area respectively. The yield point was taken as the point where the load passes through a maximum or an apparent ‘knee’ in the stress-strain curve if a maximum was not observed. Statistical analysis was performed to obtain the standard deviation and standard error of the mean of a particular data set.

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

A three dimensional finite element model consisting of a square array of fibres surrounding by matrix is employed using ANSYS 8.1 to study the stress concentration phenomena. The representative unit cell as shown in Fig. 3 is the smallest section of a unidirectional fibre composite. The fibre volume fraction of 50% was introduced into the model by adjusting the distance between the fibres in accordance with the fibre diameter. A fibre-break was replicated by removing the first row of elements from the subject fibre. The model was meshed with eight node solid 45 structural brick elements. The refinement of the model is concentrated at the front face where the strain gradient is larger compared to the distant elements at the fibre broken end.

In boundary conditions, the front face was displaced axially to 1%, whilst the back face was constrained with $U_Z=0$. X and Y axis were constrained with $U_Y=0$ and $U_X=0$ respectively, to maintain model continuity.

In this study the digitised stress-strain curve of MY0510/DDS tested at different temperatures have been used in the model whereas the properties of the carbon fibre are taken from Ref. [3].

Fig. 3. Schematic of the FE unit cell showing a simulated fibre break in fibre (A) and the position of the neighbouring fibre (B).

RESULTS

Compression test

The typical compressive stress-strain behaviour of MY0510/DDS as a function of temperature has been shown in Fig. 4. The stress initially increases proportionally to strain according to Hook's law before passing through a maximum point known as the yield. These glassy polymers proved to be extensively ductile up to the compressive strain of 40%, which is the major advantage of the uniaxial compression test in comparing to other test methods for obtaining a complete stress-strain curve.

Fig. 4. True compressive strain-stress curves of MY0510/DDS at a range of temperatures and the strain rate of $1.67 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$

Increasing the test temperature led to a considerable decrease in the yield stress and yield strain. Furthermore, although the range of test temperatures was so selected that the resin remained in a glassy state, the compressive modulus also decreased with temperature.

The variation of the yield strength and modulus of the epoxy resin with temperature is tabulated in Table 2. It is seen that these properties decrease linearly with increase in test temperature [19]. As indicated in Table 2 the estimated standard errors are very small compared to the magnitude of the yield strength and modulus.

Table 2. Compressive yield stress (σ_{cy}) and initial modulus (E_c) of MY0510/DDS at the range of temperatures and the strain rates of $1.67 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Temperature (°C)	22	70	100	140	180
σ_{cy} (MPa)	178.6 ± 1.2	137.6 ± 0.8	113.9 ± 0.9	94.2 ± 0.6	72.0 ± 0.5
E_c (MPa)	4101 ± 6	3775 ± 26	3446 ± 19	3058 ± 8	2649 ± 19

Because of the viscoelastic nature of polymers, lowering the strain rate at a constant temperature leads to a decrease in yield strength, as shown in Fig. 5. Although the range of

applied strain rate is rather narrow because of the testing limitations, the decrease in compressive yield strength is clear.

Fig. 5. Stress-strain behaviour of MY0510/DDS at a range of strain rates and the temperature of 22°C.

Finite element modelling

The model with a fibre volume fraction of 50%, including MY0510/DDS matrix at different temperatures with the properties shown in Fig. 4 and Table 2 is processed at the applied axial strain of 1%. In order to study the effect of matrix yielding on strain redevelopment along the broken fibre far away from the break, the axial tensile strain in the fibre centre was studied. The reinforcing strain in the fibre away from the fibre-break is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Axial tensile strain at the centre of the broken fibre (fibre A) at different matrix temperatures and applied strain of 1%.

From these curves, it is apparent that the increase in matrix temperature results in a lower rate of introduction of strain to the fibre. At the lower temperatures e.g. 22°C the strain length profile is exponential whereas at higher temperatures, it is predominantly linear because of the elasto-plastic behaviour of the matrix.

The effect of a fibre-break (in fibre A) on the neighbouring fibre (fibre B) (Fig. 3) is shown in Fig. 7. The presence of the fibre-break results in an increase in the axial strain in the fibre adjacent to the broken fibre. The strain profile at the centre of the fibre B has been used to quantify the strain concentration associated with the fracture of the adjacent fibre A.

Fig. 7. Axial tensile strain at the centre of the neighbouring fibre (fibre B) at different matrix temperatures and applied strain of 1%.

The strain concentration factors can be calculated from the ratio of the maximum axial strain in the intact neighbouring fibre to the applied strain (1% in this case) at each temperature. The strain concentration factors, which are tabulated in Table 3, show a decrease with increase in temperature of the matrix. From the axial strain profiles of Fig. 7 it can be seen that a maximum is followed by a sharp decrease before reaching a virtually constant value far from the fibre-break. Moreover, as the temperature of the matrix increases, the exponential strain development along the fibre becomes linear before attaining a lower constant value at the far-field.

Table 3. Strain concentration factors at the centre of the neighbouring fibre (fibre B) as a function of temperature at the applied strain of 1%.

Temperature of the matrix (°C)	20	70	100	140	180
Stress Concentration Factor (SCF)	1.19	1.19	1.18	1.17	1.14

Thus, in the adjacent fibre, a lower stress transfer results in a reduced strain concentration factor with increase in temperature. It verifies the enhanced plastic deformation at higher temperatures as shown in Fig. 4 for neat epoxy resin specimens.

DISCUSSION

As shown in Fig. 4, the post-yielding component of a stress-strain curve consists of a reduction in stress called *strain softening* followed by an extensive cold draw plateau before being subjected to an abrupt rise in stress as *strain hardening*. It is believed that the development of the deformation zone in glassy polymers is determined by a subtle equilibrium between the amount of strain softening and strain hardening [20]. The effect of temperature on this behaviour is well defined in Fig. 4. As the temperature increases, the strain softening gradually becomes more pronounced which can be attributed to a larger plastic deformation zone caused by thermally activated molecular motion. On the other hand, as the compressive deformation develops, in accordance with the equilibrium, these excited molecules are less involved in an entangled network, which gives rise to a lower gradient strain hardening. Therefore, the molecular mobility can be verified as the key parameter of the yielding. As shown in Fig. 5, a decrease in strain rate leads to a decrease in compressive yield strength which results from the nature of the viscoelastic materials as with a high strain rate the epoxy resin exhibits more highly glassy behaviour, because the molecular deformation cannot respond at the same rate as the applied load.

In a unidirectional fibre reinforced epoxy resin composite, as the temperature of the matrix increases, the enhanced elasto-plasticity of the matrix surrounding the broken fibre results in a less efficient strain transfer back into the broken fibre since more overloading energy of the fibre fracture is already absorbed by the matrix, which undergoes a larger plastic deformation. This is in consistent with a longer ineffective length of the broken fibre as a result of increase in temperature (Fig. 6). Furthermore, the decrease in axial strain of the broken fibre far away from the fibre-break as a result of the higher temperature can be attributed to the higher energy dissipated by the matrix for plastic deformation at the vicinity of the broken fibre. In this way, a lower overload is redistributed between the neighbouring fibres after one fibre fractures, which results in their prolonged reinforcing efficiency. This is associated with the decrease in axial strain of the neighbouring fibre in the plane of the fibre-break in the broken fibre with increase in temperature as shown in Fig. 7. Hence, the fibre adjacent to a broken fibre experiences a reduction in strain concentration factor as a result of a higher temperature as shown in Table 3. For the same reason, the shifting of the far-field axial strains to the lower plateaus in the neighbouring fibre can be attributed to the occurrence of the significant shear deformation in the surrounding matrix as illustrated in Fig. 7.

CONCLUSION

The yield behaviour of a commercial model epoxy network was investigated as a function of temperature and strain rate. The compressive yield strength and modulus was observed to decrease with increase in temperature and decrease in strain rate because of viscoelastic character of glassy polymers.

In a high volume fraction fibre composite model, the yielding of the matrix dominates the strain redistribution to the intact fibres at the vicinity of a broken one. At a higher temperature, the reduced stress transfer efficiency results in a lower strain concentration factor in the neighbouring fibre. Thus, the probability of forming a multiplex of fibre-breaks (and hence a flow of critical dimensions) is reduced at higher temperatures. However, the obtained SCF values are also influenced by several parameters such as modulus, yield strength, post-yielding behaviour of the matrix. Consequently, the multi fibre FE model needs further refinement for predictive purposes.

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